

Interlaboratory Comparison of Commercial High-Resistivity Silicon Calibration Substrate at D-Band

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Abstract—This article presents an interlaboratory comparison of multiline thru-reflect-line (mTRL) on-wafer calibrations on a commercial high-resistivity silicon (HRSi) substrate at D-band frequencies (110–170 GHz). Two national metrology institutes (KRISS and PTB) measured identical calibration structures using the same probe types and techniques, enabling an in-depth analysis of spatial measurement variation and reproducibility between laboratories. Overall, the results demonstrate high consistency with repeatable measurements achieved by different operators and over multiple months, showing negligible drift and affirming the stability of the calibration process. These findings demonstrate that, when best practices are followed, on-wafer calibrations on HRSi substrates can be reliably transferred between laboratories, with residual differences being attributable to known parasitic effects and boundary-condition influences.

Index Terms—Calibration, Coplanar Waveguide (CPW), D-band, on-wafer measurement, probe effects, S-parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

ON-WAFER measurements are essential for emerging applications in quantum technology, sixth generation (6G) communications, connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs), and the Internet of Things (IoT). They are known to be challenging and ambitious, containing many different parasitic effects that degrade the accuracy of the measurements.

In recent years, considerable effort has been devoted to improving the accuracy of on-wafer measurements by identifying and analyzing various sources of error, including parasitic coupling, the effect of microwave probes, and environmental influences [1], [2], [3], [4], [5].

More recently, an interlaboratory measurement comparison involving on-wafer S-parameter measurements from 10 GHz

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Fig. 1. (a) On-wafer measurement setup at PTB. Close-up view of the chuck region at (b) PTB and (c) KRISS. (d) Calibration substrate (top: photograph, bottom: layout of the same silicon substrate showing reticle positions).

to 1.1 THz was conducted to evaluate and benchmark the accuracy of these measurements [6]. Seven laboratories were involved, each measuring an individual reference substrate fabricated from a high-resistivity silicon (HRSi) wafer from the same batch. However, despite taking a unified approach to calibration, significant differences were observed in the results of the participants. Possible reasons for this can be that each participant used an individual and different calibration substrate, as well as the aging of the HRSi substrate, and also the use of probes from different vendors.

This article presents the results of a bilateral interlaboratory on-wafer comparison of S-parameters at D-band frequencies. The comparison was conducted using the same physical calibration substrate and probes (from GGB and FormFactor) at two national metrology institutes: KRISS and PTB. Identical coplanar standards on the commercial impedance standard substrate (ISS) were measured by independent operators and instrumentation using formfactor infinity (FI) and GGB probes at three reticle positions (R2, R4, and R8), shown in Fig. 1(d). Propagation constants are analyzed to determine temporal stability, operator repeatability, spatial sensitivity, and cross-lab agreement.

II. MEASUREMENT SETUP

Table I summarizes the key measurement conditions at both sites. The first measurement was performed at KRISS

TABLE I

SUMMARY OF MEASUREMENT CONFIGURATIONS USED AT KRISS AND PTB, INCLUDING CHUCK SIZE, PROBE TYPE, AND CALIBRATION SUBSTRATE

	Measurement at KRISS	Measurement at PTB
Chuck	Alumina chuck 20 mm × 20 mm × 15 mm	Alumina chuck 4 in. diameter (≈101.6 mm)
Prober	MPI TS2000-SE	MPI TS-150
VNA	Agilent Technologies PNA E8361A	Rohde and Schwarz ZNA43
Frequency extenders	VDI module 110-170 GHz	VDI module 110-170 GHz
Calibration substrate	ISS-172-887	
Probe	GGB probe (pitch = 75 μm) Formfactor Infinity Probe (pitch = 100 μm)	

Fig. 2. Measured attenuation constant α and normalized phase constant β/β_0 of R4 using FI probes at KRISS over a three-month period.

[Fig. 1(c)] using the setup described in [7]. The silicon calibration substrate (ISS-172-887), which has a relative permittivity of 11.8, was placed on a small 20 × 20 × 15 mm alumina chuck.

The second measurement was carried out at PTB [Fig. 1(a)] under comparable conditions. Although the same substrate and probes were used, a significantly larger 100 mm-diameter alumina chuck, mounted on a metallic base, was employed to assess the impact of chuck size, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

To ensure consistency, the intermediate frequency bandwidth (IFBW) was set to 100 Hz for both labs. To eliminate variability caused by different calibration algorithms, the two laboratories used an identical implementation of the multiline thru-reflect-line (mTRL) algorithm [8].

III. ANALYSIS OF MEASUREMENT RESULTS

In all figures where Δ values are shown, Δ denotes the deviation of each measurement from the mean of all corresponding measurements at each frequency point, which serves as a statistical reference.

A. Long-Term Stability and Probe Placement

To investigate substrate aging due to native silicon oxidation [9], we conducted long-term measurements over a period of three months. Fig. 2 shows repeated measurements of reticle R4 using FI probes at KRISS during this time. The attenuation constant (α) and normalized phase constant (β/β_0) remained remarkably stable, with variations of less than 0.04 dB/mm

Fig. 3. Measured attenuation constant α and normalized phase constant β/β_0 of R4 using GGB probes at KRISS over a three-month period.

Fig. 4. Measured attenuation constant α and normalized phase constant β/β_0 for positions (a) R2, (b) R4, and (c) R8, using identical GGB probes at both KRISS and PTB.

and ± 0.002 , respectively. Fig. 3 shows measurements taken on four separate dates after the FI probes were replaced by GGB probes. Once again, the results demonstrate high consistency, with all traces nearly overlapping. These results confirm that the calibration substrate is highly stable with respect to both time and probe replacement.

B. Measurement Comparison at KRISS and PTB

This section examines whether these consistent results can be achieved in two different laboratories and by different operators.

Fig. 4 shows a comparison of the measurements taken at reticles R2, R4, and R8. Identical GGB probes were used for these measurements at both KRISS and PTB. The attenuation and normalized phase constants are closely matched across all positions, with differences limited to ± 0.02 dB/mm for α and ± 0.002 for β/β_0 .

Fig. 5 summarizes the results from positions R2, R4, and R8 at KRISS and PTB. Although there are minor variations between positions, the overall consistency confirms the high

Fig. 5. Summary of measured attenuation constant α and normalized phase constant β/β_0 for positions R2, R4, and R8 using identical GGB probes at both KRISS and PTB.

Fig. 6. Comparison of attenuation constant α and normalized phase constant β/β_0 performed by two different operators using the same GGB probes. (a) Results at R2 measured at PTB. (b) Results at R4 measured at KRISS.

repeatability and reliability of the calibration when GGB probes are used in different locations and laboratories.

In Fig. 6, measurements are taken by two different operators using the same GGB probes at PTB (R2) and KRISS (R4). The near-identical results in both α and β/β_0 indicate that the mTRL calibration procedure is highly robust with respect to operator variation.

C. Impact of Probes and Positioning

Finally, we investigated the impact of probes and chuck size. The GGB probes are replaced by the FI probes. In Fig. 7, the results of measurements with FI probes at KRISS are plotted for positions R2, R4, and R8. The R4 data show significantly larger deviations, indicating that the propagation characteristics vary more strongly with the position on the calibration substrate.

In contrast, Fig. 8 shows the corresponding measurements at PTB with the same probes. Here, the spatial variation in the attenuation constant is significantly lower. Compared to the KRISS results shown in Fig. 7, the deviations across reticle positions are much smaller. This suggests that the influence of the location of the calibration substrate is reduced under the measurement conditions at PTB, where the 100 mm diameter chuck is significantly larger than the $20 \times 20 \times 15$ mm chuck at KRISS. This indicates that factors in the measurement

Fig. 7. Measured attenuation constant α and normalized phase constant β/β_0 of R2, R4, and R8 using FI probes at KRISS.

Fig. 8. Measured attenuation constant α and normalized phase constant β/β_0 of R2, R4, and R8 using the same FI probes at PTB.

environment (e.g., ceramic chuck size, device, and grounding) can influence the degree of position-dependent effects on the substrate.

IV. CONCLUSION

This article presents the results of a comparative measurement of HRSi-Coplanar Waveguide (CPW) calibration substrates at D-band frequencies by two well-established national measurement institutes, KRISS and PTB, which showed good agreement in terms of temporal stability, operator repeatability, and spatial sensitivity. However, it was found that the influence of the size of the alumina chuck is not negligible and must be taken into account when using probes that exhibit high sensitivity to the measurement environment. The underlying causes of this probe-dependent behavior will be explored in future work.

This preliminary bilateral comparison has demonstrated great potential for reliable reproducibility between laboratories for on-wafer S-parameter measurements with the same physical probes, calibration substrates, and an identical algorithm implementation.

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